

Manifestations of Home – Report.

‘Manifestations of Home’ was a pilot project to encourage and skill up Donaghmore Historical Society in DIY film and oral history recording. The project was a partnership between Rural Community Network, Mellon Centre for Migration Studies, PRONI, Northern Ireland Screen and Ulster University. All of these partners bring vital expertise and knowledge to a heritage project here in Northern Ireland. It allowed the surrounding communities of Donaghmore to explore the ‘manifestations of home’ and what home means to rural communities today. For some people home is the building they live in, for others it is a feeling, and to some it means being surrounded by the people they cherish the most.

This project was an opportunity for rural communities to explore what home means today and provided an opportunity to archive rural people’s stories, an opportunity that is very rare, unless your local community have the equipment. We placed an importance on how stories will tell they story of the local area, the place, the people, the traditions (modern and old) and how in 50,100 years’ time, they show a record of life which is really important in this digital age.

Where it started

The idea came to fruition from conversations that all the partners have been involved in which surround the need for rural communities to be provided more opportunities to record, save, protect and archive their history in the form of oral recording and video with a focus on contemporary collecting and archiving. The theme of ‘home’ was important, as in Northern Ireland, we have strong, vibrant collections in organisations such as NI Screen, PRONI, Mellon Centre for Migration Studies, National Museums NI, Linen Hall Library, that illustrate how life was lived here in Northern Ireland in the past, but not as well documented in present day.

The Community

Donaghmore Historical Society was the chosen community group as they had been making progress engaging a younger generation in the local area. We were keen this project had an intergenerational focus with both older people and young people sharing stories together. At RCN, we were also keen to work with a historical society, as here in Northern Ireland, they tend to have members who are of an older generation, and we have been working with other groups on how to diversify you audience. They are also a rural community who have a fantastic archive and recently employed a young person to start archiving their work.

Skills development and Student involvement

Our partnership with Ulster University, allowed the project to utilise the knowledge and skills of the Cinematic Arts department at Magee University, Derry. Laura Aguiar, Lecturer in Cinematic Arts, provided a linkage to a group of her students out on a placement year setting up their own company called 'Wee Donkey Productions'. Not only was this an opportunity for the community to learn from the students, but this also gave the students practical, real life experience working in rural communities and learning the challenges they face daily. The students developed the training programme for the community and were delivering their own tailored programme out in the community which was a unique opportunity for them. The community gained skills in generating questions for oral history recording, how to record using your phone and oral history recording training.

The Workshops and Programme.

The participants took part in 4 sessions at Donaghmore Historical Society's venue. Each session allowed the group to get to know each, verbally share each other's stories and ideas for the project and connect with one another over their local heritage. The participants ranged from 17-70+ yrs of age. There was a mixture of female and male participants. The first session was a very vibrant evening of stories and everyone getting to know each other. There were intimate stories of the meaning of home shared where one lady shared her experience of growing up in a Mother and Baby's home. Others shared the smell, taste and objects that made them think of home. The young people shared their experiences of leaving home to go to university which was in contrast to the older participants who described what it was like leaving

home to go work in England or America. It was very clear from this first session that there were many stories to record. Each session the participants learned or gained knowledge about oral history recording. The workshops were programmed to equip this organisation with the skills for future recording and knowing how to confidently develop an oral history recording session for their members and community.

As a group, we had a brilliant field trip visit to the Public Records Office of Northern Ireland, based in Belfast. The group were able to travel together on bus which was really important for a rural community. Transport and lack of public transport options in rural areas here, mean rural communities do not have the same access to heritage sites as city dwellers. As we entered the building, the group were very excited and delighted that a reconstructed replica of Donaghmore high cross, standing at over five metres tall, was situated at the entrance. It was a powerful start to the day as a lot of them had positive memories of the high cross. It was important as for them, it showed how an institution based in Belfast, values the heritage of their rural community. The day comprised of an introduction to who PRONI are, what they do, and how the public can get involved and use their resources. We were treated to a behind the scenes tour of the archives and stores, an experience the public would not easily get. The participants were really thankful for the opportunity to see national archives and learn how they are protected. The participants left PRONI with a deeper understanding of the importance of archives and that their stories are worth recording for future generations to come. We were also intending to have a visit to Mellon Centre for Migration Studies, but unfortunately the weather impacted our visit.

Final Film

The participants worked with the students to orally record their stories over two full day sessions and it was agreed that the students would create a visual animation that would illustrate their stories. Some of the participants are young people wanting to study film studies at University, so they were also able to get some experience of the technical side of filming.

The project had some setbacks with weather and sicknesses, so it has meant that the final animation film will be showing in two weeks' time. We will be creating a small cinema event at the communities venue and inviting the partners and wider community along with the participants family and friends. We know this project has had a positive effect on the group and wider community as there is a deeper understanding of the importance of oral history recording and this is evident in the report that Donaghmore has provided.

Conclusion

This project provided RCN with the opportunity to test the water on oral history recording in a creative way utilising the skills of students here in NI. It has shown us the positive interest that people have for storytelling and how stories can be unleashed and discovered in rural areas. The project locally for Donaghmore, opened up new conversations on stories from people locally, but also the diaspora of Donaghmore who are situated all over the world and this was achievable by social media. Facebook can help rural communities connect with people from all over the world that once lived in that local area and we see that time and time again. Timing was the main pressure on the project where the delivery had to happen in a short period of time and if delivering again or sharing advice with a community group, would be to lengthen out the creative and delivery time so that the final product and overall experience is enjoyable and of high quality.

For us at RCN, this project demonstrates to us the need to continue to find investment for rural communities in being able to deliver this in their rural areas affordably and resourced to make it achievable. We are dedicated to improving the opportunities for rural communities to become skilled in this area of work and on RCN's current HEARTH project, we have teamed up with folklorist Michael Fortune who will be delivering a DIY Oral History recording and map making programme in March this year. We would like to thank Glasgow University for providing RCN and all partners with this opportunity as it allowed us all to come together and experiment with an idea. It is vital work in rural areas where stories and archiving is in need of investment and support.